

Paper 14**ONLINE LEARNING- CHALLENGES AND BENEFITS****Souparnika ¹, Shwetha N S ² & Vinutha H. K ³**Faculty & Research Scholar of Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University,
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Mangalore.Orcid ID: 0000-0002-4583-0572, E-mail: vinutha.srinivasuniversity@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

With educational institutes closed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the government has been encouraging online education to achieve academic continuity. Most high-end private and public institutions have made the switch smoothly using online platforms such as Zoom, Google classrooms, Microsoft teams, etc., while many still find it a herculean task. The challenges of online education are multifaceted. It is time that we Indians, as a society, understand the realms of online education – in India, for India. Comparing face-to-face learning with online learning brings forth significant deficiencies in the online mode such as lack of human connect, absence of opportunities of collaborative learning, teacher supervision and the most glaring being lack of opportunities for hands-on learning in complex subjects such as subjects of Practical nature. Besides, amid the rush of hosting online classes the best teaching practices such as addressing learners Multiples Intelligences (MI), VARK Learning Styles and providing a differentiated learning experience have been relegated to the backburner. So, this paper concentrates on how does a Learner, an institution, a teacher, and a parent address the challenges of quality learning in online mode and how effectively they can face this Pandemic with less worries.

Key words: Covid 19, Challenges, Learner, Teacher, Parents, Institution.

1. INTRODUCTION:

With educational institutes closed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the government has been encouraging online education to achieve academic continuity. Most high-end private and public institutions have made the switch smoothly using online platforms such as Zoom, Google classrooms, Microsoft teams, etc., while many still find it a herculean task. The challenges of online education are multifaceted. It is time that we Indians, as a society, understand the realms of online education in India, for India [1]. Online education allows for learning something beyond the norm. A learner has access to unlimited topics and global experts in niche subjects – something otherwise not affordable or imaginable for many. Online programs allow people of a wide age group to learn at their own pace, without inhibitions, and without compromising on their other responsibilities. With the emergence and spread of COVID-19 in India, online education has trickled down to the most basic level schools and colleges! When asked about their experience with online teaching, a student from a college said, “The online option is a need

in this pandemic situation. It has brought education to us without us going anywhere, and it is more flexible". Probably, students are finding it a welcome change from strict schedules and long-distance commutes to attend classes [2]. For some others, who find learning in large classes intimidating, this may be a less stressful option. Many teachers are making the best of this situation by exploring new methods of teaching and assessment. This is encouraging. But the moment online education moves from an optional to the only form of learning, and that too long term, the bad and the ugly slowly become evident [3]. India is beginning to get a taste of this now. Using the internet for entertainment is common, but for online lessons is a big challenge. Teachers may not be well-versed with creating digital content, and conveying it effectively online. A sudden expectation from them to upgrade, and from students to adapt, is unfair. Body language and eye contact, which are important cues for the teacher, are difficult to perceive in an online class [4]. "I do not receive continual feedback in the form of students' reactions during online sessions, which reduces the effectiveness of teaching", says a college teacher. How many students have paid attention in a class? Of those, how many understood the lesson? Is the teaching pace alright? Are some students getting left behind? These questions arise even in traditional classrooms, but they are harder to address in online classes [5]. A parent of an 8-year-old attending a private school "There shouldn't be online classes for such young kids. Their concentration span is small and they do not pay attention after a while." Even college students seem to value the in-class physical learning experience much more than a virtual one. Many acknowledge that phones can be very distracting. In addition, science and technology programs often include hands-on laboratory sessions, dissertation projects and field trips to complement theoretical studies. Aspect of learning is severely limited in online education [6].

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To enlighten various problems and challenges faced by Students, Teachers, Parents and Management.
2. To enlighten Indian Scenario in online learning.
3. To enlist some negative impacts of Covid -19 on online learning and to put some effective Suggestions for Continuing Education during the pandemic situation.

3. METHODOLOGY:

In this study both primary and secondary data is considered. Primary data is collected through Questionnaire and through personal interview method. Questionnaire response is collected from students who are studying in Schools and College which is situated in Dakshina Kannada. Students are from various places of Dakshina Kannada and Kerala. also, Information collected from various authentic websites. Some journals and e-contents relating to Covid-19 effect on online learning and education are referred.

4. FINDINGS:

After getting the response from Students, Teachers, Parents and Institutional Heads through personal interview and Questionnaire method below are the findings in the study:

(a) Challenges of online learning to Students:

- (i) **Adaptability:** Students find it difficult to adapt sudden shift from offline mode of teaching to online mode. 70% of students out of 30 responses don't want online learning.

(ii) Internet Issue: Frequent internet issue is one more trouble which is existing in our country made 80% of students frustrated with online learning.

(iii) Head ache, eye pain, postures problem, back pain: Continues use of smart phone caused health issues like head ache, eye pain etc.

(iv) Lack of Motivation: Students feel demotivated because of not understanding the methods in online learning.

(v) Behavioural Issues: Many parents complain regarding excessive usage of smart phones will lead to behavioural issues.

(vi) Loneliness: Online learning made 60% of students in given response feel lonely because of no interaction with their friends and teachers.

(vii) Less interest in completing tasks: As there is no face-to-face discussion of learning, students showed less interest in completing their tasks given by teachers.

(viii) Less Mental Growth: Due to lack of interactions with friends and outside world students' mental growth decreased.

(ix) Not Understanding Methods: 70% of student's response online learning led to not understanding the methods of teaching used by the teachers.

(x) Interrupted Power Supply: Power supply also one main reason to failure in online learning as it needs required power supply.

(xi) Unaffordability to buy necessary devices are major concerns: Purchasing power of majority of students and their parents are very less due to the loss incurred in covid lock down and less income

Teachers:

1. Lack of response from students
2. Frequent internet issue
3. Lack of skill on electronic gadgets
4. Difficulties in work from home
5. Indian social system
6. Lack of eye contact
7. Irregularity in attendance of students
8. Lack of personal supervision
9. Fear of cheating

Parents

1. Depression
2. Trouble in sleeping
3. Mental distress
4. Children behavioural issue with use of smart phones
5. Health issues of children

Educational Institutions

1. Problems in admission
2. Irregularities in fees payment
3. Maintenance expenses
4. Lack of funds to pay salary

5. Fear of shut down

5. SUGGESTIONS:

Online education opens up a lot of possibilities for students and teachers alike. Yet, it may also widen the inequalities in the socio-economic fabric of India. All our policies and interventions with regard to online education should strive to be inclusive [7]. Good vision, sincere efforts and time will show India the way ahead.

Suggestions for the Students

(a) Adaptability: Adaptive learning is using Artificial intelligence to adjust the content according to individual needs. It helps in providing personalised courses to identify their weaknesses and strengths for better learning outcomes [8].

(b) Time Management: Time management is the most important factor in online learning. It needs time and effort for better learning outcomes [9].

(c) Seek Help: To manage time during online learning seek help from children parents, friends and families. So that they will not miss out on learning and at the same time work will be done.

(d) Avoid Multitasking: Do not try to take up multiple tasks at the same time. Complete one task at a time as it can make children work less effective and productive [10].

(e) Stay Positive: Make sure that children are positive towards online learning. Make use of the time in the best way and gain knowledge for better learning outcomes.

(f) Virtual Engagement: Children can communicate with their teachers in private to clear doubts either through virtual learning platforms or calls. Teachers might be able to help them out more clearly.

(g) Feedback: Teachers can give personalized guidance for improvement and identify children's weaknesses and strengths. Unless they receive feedback from teachers, there are chances of less improvement in children learning [11].

Suggestions for the Teachers:

(a) Engaging Students: There is a need to understand that online learning has a lot of advantages with respect to tools and interesting platforms to engage students in learning. Try to include those tools and multiple types of learning approaches such as podcasts, videos (teaching channel, own videos, live classes), discussions, various forms of text through articles and blogs, different assessment methods (tests, quizzes, assignments and projects) learning activities and collaboration for better learning outcomes [12].

(b) Time Commitment: Use a friendly tone for communicating with students to establish rapport.

(c) Communication: Give flexibility for the students when they ask for not making up to their deadlines. They must recognize the need of keeping in contact with the students and understand what kind of activities can accomplish goal. Conduct discussions for specific content for the students with the opportunity to solve the problem and learning effectively. Also providing discussion on practical questions by the students that can reduce frustration, problem-solving skills and handling technical issues [13].

(d) Assessment: Teachers must understand the type of questions students might ask and prepare FAQs for the common questions. Make sure that they give proper assignments and conduct tests at regular intervals. This can help to assess them based on their performance [14].

(e) Learning Management Systems: Teachers should have an understanding of the strong learning management system and web technologies that can help their pedagogy. Think and take advantage of the training and workshops attended during teacher training.

(f) Teaching Methods: Most important thing is to get comfortable in a virtual classroom. Find out different kinds of tools that make teaching and assessment simple and easy [15].

Suggestions for the Parents:

(a) Time management: There is a need to learn to manage time by parents, so that online learning of their children will not affect their personal work schedules.

(b) Observations: Parents should observe every now and then their children so that, they will get to know what their children are doing and can avoid behavioural issues with their children [16].

(c) Positive Thinking: There is a need to build up positive thinking among parents so that they will accept changes in learning and involve in creating interest among children.

(d) Accepting Changes: Parents should accept changes in order to comfort their children in learning through online [17].

Suggestions to the Institutions:

(a) Motivation and create interest: Institutions should take steps to motivate both Parents and Students. Motivation will lead to accept changes and to make everyone stay positive.

(b) Satisfying the Stake Holders: With proper plans and activities institutions should satisfy stake holders that they are trying optimum to provide best to the stakeholders.

(c) Filling belief: Belief is one more aspect which will make everyone involved to stay positive in this covid pandemic.

(d) Encouraging feedback: Feedback should be continuously encouraged by management so that they can analyse situations and find solutions immediately to continue the online learning smoothly [18].

6. CONCLUSION:

While learners can't wait to get back to the schools, this spell of online learning is going to leave principals and educators richer in terms of insights into what constitutes quality education and their own preparedness to deliver it. The challenges of quality online learning will be managed sooner than later due to the inherent transparency of this medium [19]. However, the real challenge would be not to slip into our old 'teacher-driven' ways and to remember and apply the learnings of this phase to enrich our regular classes post lockdown restrictions. Education is not just about subject knowledge but also about developing social skills and sportsmanship among the students, which is built over years. Relying solely on online education may hinder the holistic development of children, and many may underperform later in their professional and personal lives [20].

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